

Digital learning technology for tertiary education

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1. Introduction

Your dictionary (2019) refers digital technologies as an umbrella term for computer-based products and solutions. The Purpose of this essay is to explain further and discuss how digital learning technology may or may not be suitable for enhancing tertiary education. The essay will be slip into three parts, which will discuss each implementation of the technologies such as Virtual reality, gamification and Augmented reality, followed by recommendations on which technology is more advantageous when it comes to university education.

2.0 How can VR revolutionize higher education

2.1 Uses and implementation of VR in university education.

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2.1 Uses and Implementation of VR in university education.

At present, teachers still need help with having to explain or demonstrate real-life applications or examples from just textbook-based material. However, with the usage of VR in specific fields, teaching the subject material and authenticity of a situation can be quickly done as it is actively immersed in the activity using the concept of a virtual world. (Reynard 2017)

VR also being capable of having group shared experiences of the same reality; this is beneficial because students in a classroom can attain the same information and learning experience as someone who is not present. Allowing and enhancing group project discussion and participation from a mutual virtual shared experience. (Reynard 2017)

University of North Texas Dallas College of Law has also experimented with implementing this technology in their classrooms. The technology contributed to and enhanced the student's situational-based learning experience by recreating a virtual crime; this led to a consensus that using VR can benefit some faculties in tertiary education. (Wondracek 2019)

However, the cons of VR in tertiary education derive from the technology itself being quite expensive; this also contributes to the negligence of VR replacing traditional ways of teaching. As well, tertiary educational institutes would opt to present more cost-effective technologies. Which also provides similar efficiency results when used for teaching as VR does. (Reynard 2017).

3.0 Can the implementation of gamification, leaning and education

3.1 Perspectives of gamification tool being beneficial and non-beneficial to university learning.

Gamification and educational video game technologies have become much of contemporary tertiary education. As a tool for learning, claims and beliefs of superior technology in education disperse. (Toyama 2015).

Although many theorize that if the student's connection to the subject matter, incorporating digital games and game elements can enhance and promote learning and motivation, learners must be prepared to maintain and execute instructional material and show that teaching has taken place outside the classroom framework. However, contrary to belief, due to the same faulty gaming implantation to education learning such as GILETs, alignment of learning objectives does not correlate with the gaming experience; this leads to the belief that there are many other conjuncts, such as unfamiliarity, student discomfort and no real impact during gameplay.

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Referencing

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